

One Time Periodic Solutions of Navier-Stokes Equations using Asymptotic Stability and Bifurcations

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Abstract:

This article demonstrated an asymptotic dependability basis for the arrangements of Primitive conditions defined on a three-dimensional finite barrel-shaped space with time-subordinate compelling terms. Under a reasonable littleness presumption on the nontrivial driving terms, we get the presence of the time occasional answer for the Primitive conditions. Also, this time-occasional arrangement is asymptotically steady in L_2 sense.

Keywords: Asymptotic stability, Bifurcations, Navier-Stokes Equations

Introduction

The Primitive conditions of the huge scope sea are gotten from the Navier-Stokes conditions from Coriolis power, combined with thermal dynamic condition and saltiness diffusing-transport condition under the Boussinesq and hydrostatic approximations. From numerical perspectives, individuals were persuaded that the issue of worldwide well-posedness of solid answers for 3D gooey Primitive conditions may be as hard as the 3D Navier-Stokes conditions or considerably more difficult. For sure, by considering the hydrostatic estimation, the vertical speed in the Primitive conditions turns into a demonstrative variable due to the divergence free condition. Along these lines, the nonlinear term for the incompressible Navier-Stokes conditions has the form: velocity first-request subsidiaries of speed while the Primitive conditions have a more convoluted structure: first-request subordinations of level speed first-request subsidiaries of even speed.

The central issue is that the obscure weight (the surface weight) is basically a component of two-dimensional even factors. The creators exploit the central issue to build up the pivotal L_6 gauge for the speed in the confirmation of the worldwide well-posedness of solid arrangements. For quite a few years, asymptotic strength issues for fluid movements under different sorts of

settings have pulled in a ton of consideration. Roused by a progression of papers of Serrin, numerous creators have given to the investigation of the presence of time-occasional arrangements of Navier-Stokes conditions under different settings. We allude the intrigued perusers to on account of limited spaces and on account of unbounded areas. In, under the presumption of the presence of worldwide in time arrangements of 3d Navier-Stokes conditions, Serrin gave a widespread measure of the asymptotic soundness of the speed fields. In particular, assume the fluid with the consistency ν and maximal speed V is confined in a limited three-dimensional space with breadth d . At that point, the flow with the Reynolds number $V d/\nu$ under is asymptotically steady in L_2 sense. In a proceeded with work, Serrin demonstrated the presence of time-intermittent arrangements with period T under the further suspicions:

- (1) The driving term is time-occasional with period T , and
- (2) There exists a flow with Reynolds number under and this flow is equicontinuous in space variable forever.

The asymptotic solidness of e conditions defined on a finite tube-shaped space with time subordinate compelling terms. At the point when appropriate littleness conditions are forced on the driving terms, we demonstrate that the L_2 standard of the difference of any two in number arrangements will remain in general zero dramatically. As a rule, it is difficult to infer a rot gauge of the $L_2(M)$ standard of the difference of two discretionary flows. Be that as it may, the conditions' convection structure permits us to infer such a gauge between a subjective flow and a flow with certain diminutiveness. In this manner, we can utilize the triangle disparity to get the rot gauge of the difference of two subjective flows. At that point, we demonstrate the presence and time-intermittent arrangement under the supposition that the driving capacities are time-occasional and little. The littleness in the above explanations relies upon the $\nu_1, \nu_2, \mu_1, \mu_2$, the limit condition α and the size of the area.

As a fundamental work for investigating the asymptotic soundness of Primitive conditions with time-subordinate driving, we follow the thoughts of and demonstrate the worldwide in time presence of answers for Primitive conditions in our setting. We next exploit the uniform lemma to get the appraisals to build up a coupled framework of conventional differential imbalances referring the energy appraisals of fluid speed and the temperature work. Under a reasonable diminutiveness condition on the constraining term, the asymptotic solidness of arrangements with little beginning information is then gotten from this arrangement of differential imbalances. Under a comparative setting, in Tachim treated the presence of time-intermittent arrangements of the Primitive conditions by Galerkin's technique under a generally more grounded supposition that the warmth source is differentiable in transient variable and fulfilling some diminutiveness conditions. Notwithstanding, the creator didn't address the security issue in. In this article, we loosen up the routineness prerequisite of driving terms and we give an

asymptotic strength investigation. The thought we utilize to demonstrate the presence and uniqueness of time occasional solid arrangements depends on a Serrin's strategy, which we think all the more intelligently direct and numerically excellent. It is worth-referenced that our investigation can be applied to two-dimensional Navier-Stokes conditions combined with heat diffusion conditions on limited areas. It should be simple for intrigued perusers to supply the essential subtleties.

The Primitive conditions and their varieties are that we restate imbalances, uniform disparity and some significant numerical outcomes on Primitive conditions. The worldwide in time presence of the arrangement and a vital lemma are expressed and demonstrated. At long last, we state and demonstrate our primary hypotheses. Investigation for different spaces, such as the round shell area or unbounded area, should be tended to elsewhere.

MODEL EQUATION:

$$\partial v \partial t + (v \cdot \nabla)v + w \partial v \partial z + f v \perp + \nabla p = \nu \Delta v + \mu \partial^2 v + \partial z^2 + F1$$

$$\nabla p = \nu \Delta v + \mu \partial^2 v + \partial z^2 + F1 + w \partial \theta \partial z = \nu \Delta \theta + \mu \partial^2 \theta + \partial z^2 + F2$$

$$\partial v \partial z = 0$$

$$w = 0$$

$$\partial \theta \partial z = -\alpha \theta$$

on Γ_b :

$$\partial v \partial z = 0,$$

$$\partial \theta \partial z = 0$$

on Γ_l :

$$v \cdot \tilde{n} = 0,$$

$$\partial v \partial \tilde{n} \times \tilde{n} = 0, \theta = 0.$$

Here, $\alpha = 0$ is a given consistent and $\tilde{n}$ is the inward unit typical vector to Γ_l . We comment that no wind-driven limit conditions are forced on the lower surface; free-slip and no warmth flux limit conditions are forced on the horizontal limit and base, as well. The underlying condition viable is given by:

$$(v, \theta)(0) = (v_0, \theta_0).$$

$$w(x, y, z, t) = -Z z - h \nabla \cdot v(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi + \partial v \partial t + (v \cdot \nabla)v$$

$$p(x, y, z, t) = p_0(x, y, t) - Z z - h \theta(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi$$

$$\partial v \partial t + (v \cdot \nabla)v - (Z z - h \nabla \cdot v(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi) \partial v \partial z + f v \perp$$

$$+ \nabla p_0 - \nabla (Z z - h \theta(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi)$$

$$= \nu \Delta v + \mu \partial^2 v + \partial z^2 + F1$$

$$\partial \theta \partial t + (v \cdot \nabla)\theta - (Z z - h \nabla \cdot v(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi) \partial \theta \partial z = \nu \Delta \theta + \mu \partial^2 \theta + \partial z^2 + F2,$$

$$\partial v \partial z = 0$$

$$v = 1 h Z 0 - h v(x, y, z, t) dz, \tilde{v} = v - \tilde{v}.$$

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

We comment that the variation $\bar{v}$ is meant to the barotropic mode and the variable $\tilde{v}$ is signified to the barochostic mode. As have been seen in we see that $\bar{v}$ and $\tilde{v}$ fulfill the accompanying conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial \bar{v} \partial t + (\bar{v} \cdot \nabla) \bar{v} + (\tilde{v} \cdot \nabla) \tilde{v} + (\nabla \cdot \tilde{v}) \tilde{v} + f \bar{v} \perp + \nabla p_0 - \\ & Z z - h \nabla \theta(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi = \bar{v} \bar{v} + \bar{F}1, \\ & \bar{v} \cdot \bar{n} | \partial M_0 = 0, \\ & \partial \tilde{v} \partial t + (\tilde{v} \cdot \nabla) \tilde{v} - (Z z - h \nabla \cdot \tilde{v} v(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi) \partial \tilde{v} \partial z \tilde{v} + \bar{F}1, \\ & + (\tilde{v} \cdot \nabla) \bar{v} + (\bar{v} \cdot \nabla) \tilde{v} - (\tilde{v} \cdot \nabla) \tilde{v} + (\nabla \cdot \tilde{v}) \tilde{v} f \bar{v} \perp \\ & - h \nabla \theta(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi + Z z - h \nabla \theta(x, y, \xi, t) d\xi \bar{v} \bar{v} + \bar{F}1, \\ & = v14\tilde{v} + \mu1 \partial \tilde{v} \partial z + \tilde{F}1, \partial \tilde{v} \partial z \end{aligned}$$

Notice that there are three differences between our presumptions from those introduced in. To start with, rather than a Neumann limit condition, we force a Dirichlet limit state of temperature work θ on the horizontal limit Γu . The explanation is that we need a Poincare imbalance of θ on Γu for $L^4(M)$ gauge of $\partial \theta / \partial z$. Also, while we let F be time subordinate, the creators of, let $F_1 = 0$ and F_2 be time free. Third, for the underlying information, other than the condition, we add the suppositions and. The nearby presence and uniqueness of the solid answer for $F \in L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M))$ have been demonstrated:

$$\begin{aligned} |\theta_3 z|_{L^4} &= |\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^6} \leq (|\theta_2 z|_{L^2} + |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{L^2}) \leq \\ |\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^4} + \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} + \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z z dM & |\theta_3 z|_{L^2} = |\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^3} \leq \\ c \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} + \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\partial \theta_2 z \partial z|_{2dM} & L^2(\Gamma u) = \\ |\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^3(\Gamma u)} \leq c \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} & |\theta_2 z|_{1/3 H^1(\Gamma u)}^{3/2} \leq \\ \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} & (|\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^4(\Gamma u)} + |\theta_2 z|_{1/3 L^2(\Gamma u)})^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma u) + \\ |\theta_2 z|_{3/2 L^4(\Gamma u)} & |\theta_2 z|_{1/3 L^2(\Gamma u)}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} |\int_{\partial M} (v z \cdot \nabla) \theta_3 z dM| &\leq |v z|_{L^4} |\nabla \theta_3 z|_{L^2} |\theta_3 z|_{L^4} \leq |v z|_{L^4} |\nabla \theta_3 z|_{L^2} |\theta_3 z|_{L^4} + \\ \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} + \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z z dM & (\nabla \cdot v) \theta_4 z dM \leq |\nabla v|_{L^2} |\theta_2 z|_{L^4} |\theta_3 z|_{L^4} \leq \\ |\nabla v|_{L^2} |\theta_2 z|_{L^4} & \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} + \\ \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z & , |\int_{\partial M} \partial F_2 \partial z \theta_3 z dM| \leq |\partial F_2 \partial z|_{L^2} |\theta_3 z|_{L^2} \leq \\ c |\partial F_2 \partial z|_{L^2} & \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta_2 z|_{2dM} + \\ \int_{\partial M} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z z dM & 3/4, |\int_{\Gamma u} F_2 \theta_3 z dM_0| \leq \\ c |F_2|_{L^2(\Gamma u)} & |\theta_3 z|_{L^4(\Gamma u)} + |\theta_2 z|_{L^4(\Gamma u)} |\theta_2 z|_{1/2 L^2(M)}, \leq \\ c |F_2|_{L^2(\Gamma u)} & |\theta_2 z|_{L^4(\Gamma u)} + v_2 |\theta_2 z|_{L^2(\Gamma u)} + c |F_2|_{L^2(\Gamma u)}. \end{aligned}$$

As for the estimate of ∇v in $L^2(M)$, by taking $L^2(M)$ inner product of with $-4v$ and noting that

$$\begin{aligned} |\int_{\partial M} (v \cdot \nabla) v \cdot 4v dM| &\leq |v|_{L^6} |4v|_{L^3} |\nabla v|_{L^3} \leq c |v|_{L^6} |4v|_{L^3} |\nabla v|_{L^3} \\ |\nabla \partial v \partial z|_{1/2 L} &\leq v_1 |4v|_{L^2} + \mu_1 |\nabla \partial v \partial z|_{L^2} + c |v|_{L^6} |\nabla v|_{L^2}, \end{aligned}$$

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

$$|ZM_{x001} \nabla z - h \nabla \cdot v \, d\xi \partial v \, \partial z \cdot 4v \, dM| \leq c ZM_{x001} Z_0 - h |\nabla v| d\xi Z_0 - h |\partial v \, \partial z| |4v| d\xi dx dy \leq c |\nabla v|^{1/2} L |\partial v \, \partial z|^{1/2} L |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^{1/2} L^2 |4v|^{3/2} L^2 \leq v_1 10 |4v|^2 L^2 + c |\nabla v|^2 L^2 |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2 |\partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2,$$

$$\begin{aligned} |ZM \nabla_{x0012} \nabla z - h \theta d\xi 4v \, dM| &\leq ZM(Z_0 - h |\nabla \theta| d\xi) |4v| dM \leq c |\nabla \theta| L^2 |4v| L^2 \leq v_1 10 |4v|^2 L^2 + c |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2, \\ |ZM f v \perp 4v dM| &\leq c |v|^2 L^2 + 1 10 |4v|^2 L^2, \\ |ZM F_1 (-4v) dM| &\leq c |F_1| L^2 |4v| L^2 \leq v_1 10 |4v|^2 L^2 + c v_1 |x0012 \nabla z - h \theta d\xi 4v \, dM| \leq ZM(Z_0 - h) \end{aligned}$$

we reach

$$\begin{aligned} &d \, dt |\nabla v|^2 L^2 + v_1 |4v|^2 L^2 + \mu_1 |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2 \\ &\leq c(1 + |v|^4 L^6 + |\partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2 |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2) |\nabla v|^2 L^2 + c |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2 \\ &+ c |F_1|^2 L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)) |\nabla v|^2 L^2 + Z t_0_{x0012} v_1 |4v|^2 L^2 \\ &+ \mu_1 |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2 s \leq J_6(t), \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$J_6(t) = e c(1 + J_2^4 + J_2/3^3 + J_2^5) t_{x0010} |v_0|^2 H_1(M)^2 + c J_1(t) t$$

$$\begin{aligned} |ZM v \cdot \nabla \theta (4\theta + \partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2) dM| &\leq c ZM |v| |\nabla \theta| (|4\theta| + |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2|) dM \\ &\leq c |v| L^6 (|4\theta| L^2 + |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2) |\nabla \theta| L^3 \\ &\leq c |v| L^6 (|4\theta| L^2 + |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2) |\nabla \theta|^{1/2} L^2 (|4\theta \nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^{1/2} L^2) \\ &\leq v_2 6 |4\theta|^2 L^2 + v_2 + \mu_2 4 |\nabla \partial v \, \partial z|^2 L^2 + \mu_2 6 |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2 \\ &+ c |v|^4 L^6 |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2, \\ |ZM_{x0012} \nabla z - h \nabla \cdot v \, d\xi \partial \theta \, \partial z (4\theta + \partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2) dM| \\ &\leq ZM_{x0012} Z_0 - h |\nabla v| d\xi Z_0 - h |\partial \theta \, \partial z| (|4\theta| \\ &+ |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2|) d\xi dM_0 \\ &\leq c |\nabla v 4v|^{1/2} L^2 |\partial \theta \, \partial z|^{1/2} L^2 |\nabla \partial \theta \, \partial z|^{1/2} L^2 (|4\theta| L^2 \\ &+ |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2) \\ &\leq v_2 6 |4\theta|^2 L^2 + \mu_2 6 |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2|^2 L^2 + \mu_2 \\ &+ v_2 4 |\nabla \partial \theta \, \partial z|^2 L^2 c |\nabla v|^2 L^2 |4v|^2 L^2 |\partial \theta \, \partial z|^2 L^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} |ZM F_2 (4\theta + \partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2) dM| &\leq c |F_2| L^2 (|4\theta| L^2 + |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2) \\ &\leq v_2 6 |4\theta| L^2 + \mu_2 6 |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2| L^2 + c |F_2|^2 L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)), \end{aligned}$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &+ d \, dt_{x0012} |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2 + |\partial \theta \, \partial z|^2 L^2 + \alpha |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2 (\Gamma u) + v_1 |4\theta|^2 L^2 + (v_1 \\ &+ \mu_1)_{x0012} |\nabla \partial \theta \, \partial z|^2 L^2 + \alpha |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2 (\Gamma u) + \mu_1 |\partial^2 \theta \, \partial z^2|^2 L^2 \\ &\leq c |v|^4 L^6 + |\nabla v|^2 L^2 |4v|^2 L^2_{x0012} |\nabla \theta|^2 L^2 + |\partial \theta \, \partial z|^2 L^2 \\ &+ c |F_2|^2 L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \leq (\|\theta_2\|_{L^2} + \|\nabla^3 \theta_2\|_{L^2}) \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \\
 & \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} = \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \\
 & \leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) = \\
 & \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^3}(\Gamma_u) \leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^3}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_2\|_{L^1}^{1/3} H^1(\Gamma_u)^{3/2} \leq \\
 & \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2|^{4/3} \, dL^4(\Gamma_u) (\|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \|\theta_2\|_{L^1}^{1/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}^{1/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u). \\
 & |\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \theta_3 \cdot \nabla \theta_2) \, dM| \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \\
 & \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM (\nabla \cdot \nabla \theta_3) \, dM \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \\
 & \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + (\int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM) \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}^{1/2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(M), \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \nu \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u).
 \end{aligned}$$

Gronwall inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} + \|\partial \theta_2\|_{L^2} + \alpha \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + \nu \int_0^t \|\theta_2\|_{L^2} \, ds + \int_0^t (\nu_1 + \\
 & \mu_1) \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} \, ds + \alpha \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + \mu_1 \|\partial \theta_2\|_{L^2} \, ds \leq \\
 & J_7(t), \quad (3.51) \text{ where } J_7(t) = \\
 & ec(1 + J_2 + J_3) t + J_6(t) \|\theta_2\|_{H^1}(M) + \\
 & ct \|\theta_2\|_{L^\infty}(0, T; L^2(M)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} = \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \leq (\|\theta_2\|_{L^2} + \|\nabla^3 \theta_2\|_{L^2}) \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \\
 & \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} = \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \\
 & \leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) = \\
 & \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^3}(\Gamma_u) \leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^3}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_2\|_{L^1}^{1/3} H^1(\Gamma_u)^{3/2} \leq \\
 & \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2|^{4/3} \, dL^4(\Gamma_u) (\|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \|\theta_2\|_{L^1}^{1/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}^{1/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u). \\
 & |\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \theta_3 \cdot \nabla \theta_2) \, dM| \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \\
 & \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM (\nabla \cdot \nabla \theta_3) \, dM \leq \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \\
 & \|\nabla \theta_3\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + (\int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM) \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla \theta_2| \, dM + \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 \nabla^2 \theta_2| \, dM \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}^{1/2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(M), \leq \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma_u) + \nu \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma_u).
 \end{aligned}$$

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle (v \cdot \nabla)u - Zz - h\nabla \cdot v \, d\xi \partial u \partial z | u \rangle_{2u} = 0, \langle v^4 u + \mu^2 \partial^2 u \partial^2 z | u \rangle_{2u} = \\ & -ZMv^2 |u|^2 |\nabla u|^2 + \mu^2 |u|^2 |\partial u \partial z| + v^2 |\nabla u|^2 + \mu^2 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |2dM, \\ & \langle fu \perp, |u \rangle_{2u} = 0, |ZM[(u \cdot \nabla)v - (\nabla \cdot v)u] \cdot |u \rangle_{2udM} \leq \\ & c |ZM|v| |\nabla u| |u|^3 dM \leq c ||\nabla u||u||L^2 ||u|^2 |L^3 |v|L^6 \leq c ||\nabla u||u||L^2 ||u|^2 |1/ \\ & 2 L^2_{x0012} |\nabla u|^2 |1/2 L^2 + |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |1/2 L^2 + ||u|^2 |1/2 L^2 |v|L^6 \\ & = c ||\nabla u||u||L^2 |u|^4_{x0012} |\nabla u|^2 |1/2 L^2 + |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |1/2 L^2 + |u|^4 |v|L^6 \leq \\ & c (|v|^2 L^6 + |v|^4 L^6) |u|^4 L^4 + v^4 ||\nabla u||u|^2 L^2 + v^8 |\nabla u|^2 |2 L^2 + \\ & \mu^8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |2 L^2, | \theta^3 z |L^4 = |\theta^2 z |3/2 L^6 \leq (|\theta^2 z |L^2 + |\nabla^3 \theta^2 z |L^2) \leq \\ & |\theta^2 z |3 L^4 +_{x0010} ZM \theta^2 z |\nabla \theta^2 z |2dM + ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM^3 |\theta^3 z |L^2 = |\theta^2 z |3/ \\ & 2 L^3 \leq c_{x0010} |\theta^2 z |3 L^4 + ZM \theta^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & z |\nabla \theta^2 z |2dM + ZM \theta^2 z |\partial \theta^2 z \partial z |2dM L^2(\Gamma u) = |\theta^2 z |3/2 L^3(\Gamma u) \leq \\ & c_{x0010} |\theta^2 z |3 L^3(\Gamma u) |\theta^2 z |1/3 H^1(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq_{x0010} |\theta^4 z |4/3 L^4(\Gamma u) (|\theta^2 z | \\ & 3 L^4(\Gamma u) + |\theta |\nabla \theta| |1/3 L^2(\Gamma u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma u) + |\theta|^2 L^4(\Gamma u) |\theta |\nabla \theta| |1/2 L^2(\Gamma u). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & |ZM(vz \cdot \nabla) \theta^3 z dM| \leq |vz|^4 |\nabla \theta|^2 |\theta^3 z |L^4 \leq |vz|^4 |\nabla \theta|^2 |z|^3 L^4 + \\ & ZM \theta^2 z |\nabla \theta^2 z |2dM + ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM (\nabla \cdot v) \theta^4 z dM| \leq |\nabla v|^2 |\theta^2 z |L^4 |\theta^3 z |L^4 \leq \\ & |\nabla v|^2 |\theta^2 z |L^4_{x0010} |\theta^3 z |L^4 + (ZM \theta^2 z |\nabla \theta^2 z |2dM + \\ & ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z, |ZM \partial^2 \partial z \theta^3 z dM| \leq |\partial^2 \partial z |L^2 |\theta^3 z |L^2 \leq \\ & c |\partial^2 \partial z |L^2_{x0010} |\theta^3 z |3 + ZM \theta^2 z |\nabla \theta^2 z |2dM + \\ & ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM^3/4, |Z\Gamma u F^2 \theta^3 dM^0| \leq \\ & c |F^2 |L^2(\Gamma u) \theta^3 L^4(\Gamma u) + |\theta|^2 L^4(\Gamma u) |\theta |\nabla \theta| |1/2 L^2(M), \leq \\ & c |F^2 |L^2(\Gamma u) \theta^4 L^4(\Gamma u) + v^2 |\theta |\nabla \theta| |2 L^2(\Gamma u) + c |F^2 |2 L^2(\Gamma u) + \\ & c |F^2 |L^2(\Gamma u) \partial F^1 \partial z \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & |u \rangle_{2u} \leq |\partial F^1 \partial z |L^2 ||u|^3 |L^2 = |\partial F^1 \partial z |L^2 ||u|^2 |3/2 L^3 \leq \\ & c |\partial F^1 \partial z |L^2_{x0012} ||u|^2 |1/2 L^2 (|\nabla u|^2 |1/2 L^2 + |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |1/2 L^2)^{3/2} \leq \\ & c |\partial F^1 \partial z |L^2 ||u|^3 |2 L^4 (|\nabla u|^2 |3/4 L^2 + |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |3/4 L^2) \leq \\ & v^8 |\nabla u|^2 |2 L^2 + \mu^8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |2 L^2 + c |\partial F^1 \partial z |8/5 L^2 ||u|^2 |12/5 L^4 \leq \\ & v^8 |\nabla u|^2 |2 L^2 + \mu^8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |2 L^2 + c |\partial F^1 \partial z |L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2) + \\ & |\partial F^1 \partial z |2 L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2) |u|^4 L^4, \\ & |ZM \nabla \theta \cdot |u \rangle_{2udM} \leq c |ZM \theta| |\nabla u| |u|^2 dM \leq c |\theta|^4 |u|^4 ||u| |\nabla u| |L^2 \leq \\ & v^4 ||u| |\nabla u| |2 L^2 + c |\theta|^2 L^4 + |\theta|^2 L^4 |u|^4 L^4. \end{aligned}$$

L^4 Estimate for $\partial v / \partial z$ To fill the second gap, we need to perform $L^4(M)$ estimate of $\partial v / \partial z$. For that purpose, we take $L^2(M)$ inner product of (3.44) with $|u \rangle_{2u}$ and use the following facts:

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle (v \cdot \nabla)u - Zz - h\nabla \cdot v \, d\xi \partial u \partial z, |u \rangle_{2u} = 0, \langle \\ & v^4 u + \mu^2 \partial^2 u \partial^2 z, |u \rangle_{2u} = \\ & -ZMv^2 |u|^2 |\nabla u|^2 + \mu^2 |u|^2 |\partial u \partial z| + v^2 |\nabla u|^2 + \mu^2 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |2dM, \langle \\ & fu \perp, |u \rangle_{2u} = 0, |ZM[(u \cdot \nabla)v - (\nabla \cdot v)u] \cdot |u \rangle_{2udM} \leq \end{aligned}$$

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{ZM} |v| |\nabla u| |u|^3 dM &\leq c |\nabla u| |u| |L^2| |u|^2 |L^3| |v| |L^6| \leq c |\nabla u| |u| |L^2| |u|^2 |1/2 L^2| \\
 &+ |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |1/2 L^2| + |u|^2 |1/2 L^2| |v| |L^6| = \\
 c |\nabla u| |u| |L^2| |u|^4 |L^4| &+ |u|^4 |L^4| + v^1 4 |\nabla u| |u| |L^2| + v^1 8 |\nabla u|^2 |L^2| + \\
 \mu^1 8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |L^2| &+ |\partial F_1 \partial z, |u|^2 u > | \leq |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^2| |u|^3 |L^2| = \\
 |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^2| |u|^2 |3/2 L^3| &\leq c |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^2| |u|^2 |1/2 L^2| (|\nabla u|^2 |1/2 L^2| + \\
 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |1/2 L^2|)^{3/2} &\leq c |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^2| |u|^3 |L^4| (|\nabla u|^2 |3/4 L^2| + |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |3/4 L^2|) \\
 &\leq v^1 8 |\nabla u|^2 |L^2| + \mu^1 8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |L^2| + c |\partial F_1 \partial z |8/5 L^2| |u|^2 |L^4| \\
 &\leq v^1 8 |\nabla u|^2 |L^2| + \mu^1 8 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |L^2| + c |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2)| + \\
 |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2)| &|u|^4 |L^4|, |ZM \nabla \theta \cdot |u|^2 u dM| \leq \\
 c_{ZM} |\theta| |\nabla u| |u|^2 dM &\leq c |\theta| |L^4| |u|^4 |u| |\nabla u| |L^2| \leq v^1 4 ||u| |\nabla u| |L^2| + \\
 c |\theta|^2 |L^4| + |\theta|^2 |L^4| &|u|^4 |L^4|,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\theta^3 z| |L^4| = |\theta^2 z| |3/2 L^6| &\leq (|\theta^2 z| |L^2| + |\nabla \theta^2 z| |L^2|) \leq \\
 |\theta z| |3 L^4| + |ZM \theta^2 z| &|\nabla \theta z| |2 dM| + |ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM| |\theta^3 z| |L^2| = |\theta^2 z| |3/2 L^3| \leq \\
 c_{x0010} |\theta z| |3 L^4| &+ |ZM \theta^2 z| |\nabla \theta z| |2 dM| + |ZM \theta^2 z| |\partial \theta z \partial z |2 dM| |L^2(\Gamma u)| = \\
 |\theta^2 z| |3/2 L^3(\Gamma u)| &\leq c_{x0010} |\theta^2 z| |2/3 L^3(\Gamma u)| |\theta^2 z| |1/3 H^1(\Gamma u)|^{3/2} \leq \\
 |x0010| |\theta^4 z| |3 L^4(\Gamma u)| &(|\theta^2 z| |3 L^4(\Gamma u)| + |\theta| |\nabla \theta| |1/3 L^2(\Gamma u)|)^{3/2} \leq |L^4(\Gamma u)| + \\
 |\theta^2 z| |L^4(\Gamma u)| |\theta| |\nabla \theta| &|1/2 L^2(\Gamma u)|. |ZM(vz \cdot \nabla) \theta^3 z dM| \leq \\
 |vz| |L^4| |\nabla \theta| |L^2| &|\theta^3 z| |L^4| \leq \\
 |vz| |L^4| |\nabla \theta| |L^2| &|\theta^3 z| |L^4| + |ZM \theta^2 z| |\nabla \theta z| |2 dM| + |ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM| |\nabla \cdot v| \theta^4 z dM| \leq \\
 |\nabla v| |L^2| |\theta z| |L^4| &|\theta^3 z| |L^4| \leq |\nabla v| |L^2| |\theta z| |L^4| |x0010| |\theta z| |3 L^4| + (|ZM \theta^2 z| |\nabla \theta z| |2 dM| + \\
 |ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM|, &|ZM \partial F_2 \partial z \theta^3 z dM| \leq |\partial F_2 \partial z |L^2| |\theta^3 z| |L^2| \leq \\
 c |\partial F_2 \partial z |L^2| &|x0010| |\theta z| |3 L^4| + |ZM \theta^2 z| |\nabla \theta z| |2 dM| + \\
 |ZM \theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM| &|3/4|, |Z \Gamma u F_2 \theta^3 z dM| \leq \\
 c |F_2| |L^2(\Gamma u)| &|\theta^3 z| |L^4(\Gamma u)| + |\theta^2 z| |L^4(\Gamma u)| |\theta| |\nabla \theta| |1/2 L^2(M)|, \leq \\
 c |F_2| |L^2(\Gamma u)| &|\theta^4 z| |L^4(\Gamma u)| + v^2 |\theta| |\nabla \theta| |L^2(\Gamma u)| + c |F_2| |L^2(\Gamma u)| + \\
 c |F_2| |L^2(\Gamma u)|. &
 \end{aligned}$$

we reach

$$\begin{aligned}
 d dt |u|^4 |L^4| + 2v^1 ||u| |\nabla u| |L^2| &+ v^1 |\nabla u|^2 |L^2| + 2\mu^1 ||u| |\partial u \partial z| |L^2| + \\
 \mu^1 |\partial \partial z |u|^2 |L^2| &\leq \\
 c(|v|^2 |L^6| + |v|^4 |L^6| &+ |\theta|^2 |L^4| + |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2)|) |u|^4 |L^4| + \\
 c |\theta|^2 |L^4| + c |\partial F_1 \partial z |L^\infty(0, T; &L^2(M)^2)|. (3.52)
 \end{aligned}$$

Gronwall inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\partial v \partial z| |4 L^4| + Z t 0 v^1 ||\partial v \partial z| |\nabla \partial v \partial z| &+ v^1 |\nabla |\partial v \partial z|^2 |L^2| ds \\
 + Z t 0 \mu^1 ||\partial v \partial z| |\partial^2 v \partial^2 z| |L^2| &+ \mu^1 |\partial \partial z| (|\partial v \partial z|^2) |L^2| ds \leq J_8(t),
 \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$J_8(t) = \text{ect} + c(J_{1/6} J_{4/3} + J_2 + J_{3/2}) t_{x0012} |\partial v_0 \partial z|_4 L_4(M) + c(J_2 + |\partial F_1 \partial z|_4 L_\infty$$

Step 8. L_4 ESTIMATE FOR $\partial\theta/\partial z$ Taking L_2 inner product of the z -derivative of $(\theta z)_3$ we obtain

14

$$d dt |\theta z|_4 L_4 + 3\nu ZM\theta^2 z |\nabla\theta z|_{2dM} + 3\mu ZM\theta^2 z \theta^2 z z dM = -ZM(vz \cdot \nabla)\theta\theta^3 z dM + ZM(\nabla \cdot v)\theta^4 z dM \quad (3.54) + ZM \partial F_2 \partial z \theta^3 z dM + \mu Z\Gamma u \theta z z \theta^3 z dM_0.$$

Using the boundary situation,

$$\begin{aligned} |\theta^3 z|_{L^4} &= |\theta^2 z|_{3/2} L_6 \leq (|\theta^2 z|_{L^2} + |\nabla^3 \theta^2 z|_{L^2}) \leq \\ |\theta z|_{3} L_4 + \dots & \leq \\ c_{x0010} |\theta z|_{3} L_4 + ZM\theta^2 z |\nabla\theta z|_{2dM} + ZM\theta^2 z |\partial\theta z \partial z|_{2dM} L_2(\Gamma u) &= \\ |\theta^2|_{3/2} L_3(\Gamma u) &\leq c_{x0010} |\theta^2|_{2/3} L_3(\Gamma u) |\theta^2|_{1/3} H_1(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq \\ \dots &\leq L_4(\Gamma u) + \\ |\theta^2|_{L^4} |\theta|_{\nabla\theta} & \leq \\ |ZM(vz \cdot \nabla)\theta\theta^3 z dM| &\leq |vz|_{L^4} |\nabla\theta|_{L^2} |\theta^3 z|_{L^4} \leq \\ |vz|_{L^4} |\nabla\theta|_{L^2} & \leq \\ |\nabla v|_{L^2} |\theta z|_{L^4} &\leq |\nabla v|_{L^2} |\theta z|_{L^4} \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta z(z = 0) = -\alpha\theta(z = 0),$$

and remaining the equation on the upper boundary Γ_u , we obtain that

$$\mu Z\Gamma u \theta z z \theta^3 z dM_0 = -\alpha Z\Gamma u \theta \partial t \theta^3 - \nu^2 \theta^4 \theta^3 - F_2 \theta^3 dM_0 = -\alpha \dots$$

Next, noting that:

$$\begin{aligned} |\theta^3 z|_{L^4} &= |\theta^2 z|_{3/2} L_6 \leq (|\theta^2 z|_{L^2} + |\nabla^3 \theta^2 z|_{L^2}) \leq \\ |\theta z|_{3} L_4 + \dots & \leq \\ c_{x0010} |\theta z|_{3} L_4 + ZM\theta^2 z |\nabla\theta z|_{2dM} + ZM\theta^2 z |\partial\theta z \partial z|_{2dM} L_2(\Gamma u) &= \\ |\theta^2|_{3/2} L_3(\Gamma u) &\leq c_{x0010} |\theta^2|_{2/3} L_3(\Gamma u) |\theta^2|_{1/3} H_1(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq \\ \dots &\leq L_4(\Gamma u) + \\ |\theta^2|_{L^4} |\theta|_{\nabla\theta} & \leq \end{aligned}$$

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

$$\begin{aligned}
 |ZM(vz \cdot \nabla)\theta\theta_3 z dM| &\leq |vz|L_4|\nabla\theta|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_4 \leq |vz|L_4|\nabla\theta|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_4 + \\
 ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM(\nabla \cdot v)\theta_4 z dM &\leq |\nabla v|L_2|\theta z|L_4|\theta_3 z|L_4 \leq \\
 |\nabla v|L_2|\theta z|L_4|\theta_3 z|L_4 + (ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + \\
 ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM, |ZM \partial F_2 \partial z \theta_3 z dM| &\leq |\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_2 \leq \\
 c|\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_2 + ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + \\
 ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM^{3/4}, |Z\Gamma u F_2\theta_3 dM_0| &\leq \\
 c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u)\theta_3 L_4(\Gamma u) + |\theta|L_4(\Gamma u)|\theta|\nabla\theta||1/2 L_2(M), &\leq \\
 c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u)|\theta|L_4(\Gamma u) + v_2|\theta|\nabla\theta||2 L_2(\Gamma u) + c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u) + \\
 c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u).
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, having traced up with the theorem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_2|L_2(\Gamma u) &\leq c|F_2|L_2(M) + |\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2(M). \text{ Hence, } |Z\Gamma u F_2\theta_3 dM_0| \leq \\
 c(|F_2|L_2 + |\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2)|\theta|L_4 L_4(\Gamma u) + v_2|\theta|\nabla\theta||2 L_2(\Gamma u) + c|F_2|L_2 + \\
 c|\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2 + c|F_2|L_2 + c|\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2. \\
 |\theta_3 z|L_4 = |\theta_2 z|^{3/2} L_6 &\leq (|\theta_2 z|L_2 + |\nabla\theta_2 z|L_2) \leq \\
 |\theta z|L_4 + |\theta_2 z|^{3/2} L_6 &= |\theta_2 z|^{3/2} L_6 + ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM^{3/4}|\theta_3 z|L_2 = |\theta_2 z|^{3/2} L_6 \\
 c|\theta_2 z|^{3/2} L_6 + ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + ZM\theta_2 z|\partial\theta z \partial z|2dM L_2(\Gamma u) &= \\
 |\theta_2|^{3/2} L_6 L_3(\Gamma u) &\leq c|\theta_2|^{3/2} L_6 L_3(\Gamma u)|\theta_2|^{1/3} H_1(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq \\
 |\theta_2|^{3/2} L_6 L_3(\Gamma u)(|\theta|^{2/3} L_4(\Gamma u) + |\theta|\nabla\theta||1/3 L_2(\Gamma u))^{3/2} &\leq L_4(\Gamma u) + \\
 |\theta|L_4(\Gamma u)|\theta|\nabla\theta||1/2 L_2(\Gamma u).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |ZM(vz \cdot \nabla)\theta\theta_3 z dM| &\leq |vz|L_4|\nabla\theta|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_4 \leq \\
 |vz|L_4|\nabla\theta|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_4 + ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM(\nabla \cdot v)\theta_4 z dM &\leq \\
 |\nabla v|L_2|\theta z|L_4|\theta_3 z|L_4 \leq |\nabla v|L_2|\theta z|L_4|\theta_3 z|L_4 + (ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + \\
 ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM, |ZM \partial F_2 \partial z \theta_3 z dM| &\leq |\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_2 \leq \\
 c|\partial F_2 \partial z|L_2|\theta_3 z|L_2 + ZM\theta_2 z|\nabla\theta z|2dM + \\
 ZM\theta_2 z\theta_2 z dM^{3/4}, |Z\Gamma u F_2\theta_3 dM_0| &\leq \\
 c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u)\theta_3 L_4(\Gamma u) + |\theta|L_4(\Gamma u)|\theta|\nabla\theta||1/2 L_2(M), &\leq \\
 c|F_2|L_2(\Gamma u)|\theta|L_4(\Gamma u) + v_2|\theta|\nabla\theta||2 L_2(\Gamma u)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 F = (F_1, F_2) \in L^\infty(0, \infty; (L_2(M))^3), \partial F \in L^\infty(0, \infty; (L_2(M))^3), (v_0, \theta_0) \\
 \in V, \partial v_0 / \partial z \in (L_4(M))^2 \text{ and } \partial\theta_0 / \partial z \in L_4(M).
 \end{aligned}$$

Then basically the $\gamma^* 1$ and $\gamma^* 2$ such that for (v, θ) , the strong solution to with the initial condition (v_0, θ_0) ,

if (v_0, θ_0) and $F = (F_1, F_2)$ satisfies $|v_0|_2 H_1 + |\theta_0|_2 H_1 + |\partial v_0 \partial z|_2 L_4 + |\partial\theta_0 \partial z|_2 L_4(M) \leq \gamma^* 1$,

$|F|_2 L^\infty(0, \infty; (L_2(M))^3) + |\partial F \partial z|_2 L^\infty(0, \infty; (L_2(M))^3) \leq \gamma^* 2 \leq \gamma^* 2$,

then we have

$$\sup_{t \geq 0} |v(t)|_2 H_1 + |\theta(t)|_2 H_1 + |\partial v(t) \partial z|_2 L_4 + |\partial\theta(t) \partial z|_2 L_4 \leq C(\gamma^* 1, \gamma^* 2),$$

when (γ_1, γ_2) positive numbered property having been determined

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

Hence, by (3.66), we obtain $\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} B_1(s) ds \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), t \geq 0$. (3.69) Next, by (3.67) and the assumption (3.59), we see that $B_2(t)$ satisfies $\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} B_2(s) ds \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), t \geq 0$. Notice that $\|\tilde{v}\|_{L^6} \leq c(\|\tilde{v}\|_{L^6(M_0)} + \|v\|_{L^6}) \leq c\|v\|_{L^6} \leq \|\nabla v\|_{L^2}$.

We then derive from (3.66) that

$$\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} \|\tilde{v}\|_{L^6} ds \leq c \int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} ds \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 0.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} = \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^6}^{3/2} \leq (\|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2} + \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2}) \leq \\ & \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} dM + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2}^2 dM \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^2} = \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 / \\ & 2 L^3 \leq \\ & c \int_{\Gamma} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} dM + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2}^2 dM L^2(\Gamma u) = \\ & \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 L^3(\Gamma u) \leq c \int_{\Gamma} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 L^3(\Gamma u) \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^{1/3} H^1(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq \\ & \int_{\Gamma} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 L^4(\Gamma u) (\|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^4(\Gamma u) + \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} L^2(\Gamma u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma u) + \\ & \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^4(\Gamma u) \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} L^2(\Gamma u). \\ & |\int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \nabla \theta_2 z dM| \leq \|v z\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} \leq \\ & \|v z\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 L^4 + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} dM + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2}^2 dM (\nabla \cdot v) \theta_4 z dM \leq \\ & \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} \leq \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \int_{\Gamma} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^3 L^4 + (\int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} dM + \\ & \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2}^2 dM) \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} \leq \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \leq \\ & c \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} dM + \\ & \int_{\Gamma} \theta_2 z \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^2}^2 dM \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} \leq \\ & c \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^2(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} L^4(\Gamma u) + \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^4(\Gamma u) \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} L^2(M) \leq \\ & c \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^2(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3 z\|_{L^4} L^4(\Gamma u) + v^2 \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^2(\Gamma u) + c \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^2(\Gamma u) + c \|\theta_2 z\|_{L^4}^2 L^2(\Gamma u) \end{aligned}$$

Inferring from (3.39), by (3.69) –(3.71) and the uniform lemma, we obtain

$$\|\tilde{v}(t)\|_{L^6} \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq r. \quad (3.72)$$

Moreover, by we derive from that

$$\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} \|\tilde{v}\|_{L^6} \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} ds \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 2r.$$

the uniform lemma, we derive from that

$$\|\nabla v\|_{L^2(M_0)} \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 3r.$$

Meanwhile, we obtain $\|v\|_{L^6} \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 3r$.

Again, by the uniform Gronwall lemma, and, we derive from that $\|\partial v / \partial z\|_{L^2} \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 4r$. Moreover, it is inferred from that $\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} v \|\nabla \partial v / \partial z\|_{L^2} + \mu_1 \|\partial^2 v / \partial z^2\|_{L^2} ds \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 4r$. Inferring from (3.48), by and the uniform Gronwall lemma, we have $\|\nabla v\|_{L^2} \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 5r$.

Moreover, from, by direct integration, we have $\int_0^t \int_{\Gamma} |4v|_{L^2} dM \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 5r$. Applying the uniform lemma, we have

$$\|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2} + \|\partial \theta_2 z / \partial z\|_{L^2} + \alpha \|\nabla \theta_2 z\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 6r$$

(3.80)

Step 3. L_4 smallness. To manipulate the L_4 smallness of $\partial v / \partial z$, we have the following observations. First, due to the boundary condition $\partial v / \partial z = 0$, on Γ_b , the Poincare inequality for $\|v z\|_2$ gives the inequality

$$\|v z\|_{L^4} \leq \|\|v z\|_2\|_{L^2} \leq c \|\partial \theta_2 z / \partial z\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u). \quad (3.81)$$

We may choose γ_1 and γ_2 small so that, by (3.75) and (3.68), we have

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & c(|v|_2 L^6 + |v|_4 L^6 + |\theta|_2 L^4 + |\partial F_1 \partial z|_2 L^\infty(0, T; L^2(M)^2)) |vz|_4 L^4 \leq \\
 & C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) |\partial \partial z|_2 L^2 \leq \mu_1^2 |\partial z|_2 L^2, \forall t \geq 3r. \quad (3.82) \\
 & |\theta_3 z|_4 L^4 = |\theta_2 z|_3 L^2 \leq (|\theta_2 z|_2 L^2 + |\nabla^3 \theta_2 z|_2 L^2) \leq \\
 & |\theta z|_3 L^4 + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z dM^3 |\theta_3 z|_2 L^2 = |\theta_2 z|_3 L^4 \\
 & \leq \\
 & c \int_{\Omega} |\theta z|_3 L^4 + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\partial \theta z \partial z|_2 dM L^2(\Gamma_u) = \\
 & |\theta_2 z|_3 L^4(\Gamma_u) \leq c \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 z|_3 L^4(\Gamma_u) |\theta_2 z|_1 H^1(\Gamma_u)^{3/2} \leq \\
 & \int_{\Omega} |\theta_2 z|_4 L^4(\Gamma_u) (|\theta_2 z|_3 L^4(\Gamma_u) + |\theta|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & |\theta|_2 L^4(\Gamma_u) |\theta|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\int_{\Omega} \theta_3 z dM| \leq |vz|_4 L^4 |\nabla \theta|_2 L^2 |\theta_3 z|_4 L^4 \leq |vz|_4 L^4 |\nabla \theta|_2 L^2 |\theta_3 z|_4 L^4 + \\
 & \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z dM (\nabla \cdot v) \theta_4 z dM \leq |\nabla v|_2 L^2 |\theta z|_4 L^4 |\theta_3 z|_4 L^4 \leq \\
 & |\nabla v|_2 L^2 |\theta z|_4 L^4 \int_{\Omega} |\theta z|_3 L^4 + (\int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \\
 & \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z dM), |\int_{\Omega} \partial F_2 \partial z \theta_3 z dM| \leq |\partial F_2 \partial z|_2 L^2 |\theta_3 z|_2 L^2 \leq \\
 & c |\partial F_2 \partial z|_2 L^2 \int_{\Omega} |\theta z|_3 L^4 + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \\
 & \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z dM^{3/4}, |\int_{\Omega} F_2 \theta_3 dM| \leq \\
 & c |F_2|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u) |\theta_3 z|_4 L^4(\Gamma_u) + |\theta|_2 L^4(\Gamma_u) |\theta|_2 L^2(M), \leq \\
 & c |F_2|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u) |\theta|_4 L^4(\Gamma_u) + v_2 |\theta|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u) + c |F_2|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u) + \\
 & c |F_2|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u)
 \end{aligned}$$

By (3.82) and Gronwall inequality, we infer from (3.52) that

$$|\partial v \partial z|_2 L^4 \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 3r. \quad (3.83)$$

To proceed the L^4 smallness of $\partial \theta / \partial z$, we notice that the boundary conditions $\partial \theta \partial z = 0$ on Γ_b , $\theta = 0$ on Γ_l , give the Poincare inequalities

$$|\theta_2 z|_2 L^2 \leq c \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z \theta_2 z dM, |\theta_2 z|_2 L^2(\Gamma_u) \leq c \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta|_2 dM.$$

Now, choose γ^*_1 and γ^*_2 small enough so that for $\gamma_1 \leq \gamma^*_1$, $\gamma_2 \leq \gamma^*_2$, (3.84) we have not only (3.82) but also

$$c(|\nabla \theta|_4 L^2 + |\nabla v|_2 L^2 + |\nabla v|_4 L^2 + |F_2|_2 L^2 + |\partial F_2 \partial z|_2 L^2) (|\theta z|_4 L^4 + \alpha^3 |\theta|_4 L^4(\Gamma_u)) \leq 1 - v_2 \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta z|_2 dM + \alpha^3 \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 z |\nabla \theta|_2 dM.$$

(3.85) Hence, by (3.80), (3.78), (3.83) and Gronwall inequality, inferring from (3.57),

we obtain

$$|\theta z|_4 L^4 + \alpha^3 |\theta|_4 L^4(\Gamma_u) \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 5r, \quad (3.86)$$

provided γ_1 and γ_2 are small. Combining (3.63), (3.65), (3.80), (3.78), (3.76) and (3.83), we have

$$|v|_2 H^1 + |\partial v \partial z|_2 L^4 + |\theta|_2 H^1 + |\partial \theta \partial z|_2 L^4 \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2), \forall t \geq 6r. \quad (3.87)$$

To sum up, by (3.62) and (3.87),

$$\sup_{t \geq 0} |v|_2 H^1 + |\theta|_2 H^1 + |\partial v(t) \partial z|_2 L^4 + |\partial \theta(t) \partial z|_2 L^4 \leq C(\gamma_1, \gamma_2).$$

The proof of the lemma is complete.

4. Main Theorem and its proof

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

In this section, we state our main theorems and give the complete proofs. The first main result regarding the asymptotic stability issue is as follows. Theorem 4.1. Suppose $F = (F_1, F_2), \partial F / \partial z \in L^\infty(0, \infty; (L^2(M))^3)$. There exists a positive number $\tilde{\gamma}_2$ such that if $\|F\|_{L^\infty(0, \infty; (L^2(M))^3)} + \|\partial F / \partial z\|_{L^\infty(0, \infty; (L^2(M))^3)} \leq \tilde{\gamma}_2$, (4.1) then for any two strong solutions $(v_1(t), \theta_1(t))$ and $(v_2(t), \theta_2(t))$ of the system, we have $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|v_1(t) - v_2(t)\|_{L^2} + \|\theta_1(t) - \theta_2(t)\|_{L^2} = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} &= \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^6} \leq (\|\theta_2\|_{L^2} + \|\nabla \theta_2\|_{L^2}) \|\theta_1\|_{L^2} \\ \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_1 \, dM &+ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} = \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^6} \\ &\leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4} + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_1 \, dM + \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) = \\ &\|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{3/2} \|\theta_1\|_{L^6}(\Gamma u) \leq c \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^6}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{1/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^6}(\Gamma u)^{3/2} \leq \\ &\|\theta_2\|_{L^4}^{4/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) (\|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{2/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) + \|\theta_2\|_{L^3}^{1/3} \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u))^{3/2} \leq L^4(\Gamma u) + \\ &\|\theta_2\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_1\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_1 \, dM &\leq \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_1\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\nabla \theta_1\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} + \\ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM &+ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM (\nabla \cdot v) \theta_4 \, dM \leq \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} \leq \\ \|\nabla v\|_{L^2} \|\theta_2\|_{L^4} \|\theta_3\|_{L^4} &+ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM + \\ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM &, \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM \leq \|\theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} \leq \\ c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2} \|\theta_3\|_{L^2} &+ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM + \\ \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM &, \int_{\Omega} \theta_2 \theta_3 \nabla \theta_2 \, dM \leq \\ c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) &\|\theta_2\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u), \leq \\ c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^4}(\Gamma u) &+ \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) \|\theta_3\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) + c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u) + \\ c \|\theta_2\|_{L^2}(\Gamma u). & \end{aligned}$$

Results and Discussion

A fundamental work for investigating asymptotic soundness of Primitive conditions with time-subordinate driving, we follow the thoughts of and demonstrate the worldwide in time presence of answers for Primitive conditions in our setting. We next exploit the uniform Gronwall lemma to get the appraisals to build up a coupled framework of conventional differential imbalances concerning the energy appraisals of fluid speed and the temperature work. Under a reasonable diminutiveness condition on the constraining term, the asymptotic solidness of arrangements with little beginning information is then gotten from this arrangement of differential imbalances.

Under a comparative setting, in Tachim treated the presence of time-intermittent arrangements of the Primitive conditions by Galerkin's technique under a generally more grounded supposition that the warmth source is differentiable in the transient variable fulfilling some diminutiveness conditions. Notwithstanding, the creator didn't address the security issue in. In this article, we loosen up the routineness prerequisite of driving terms and

we give an asymptotic strength investigation. The thought we utilize to demonstrate the presence and uniqueness of time occasional solid arrangements depends on a Serrin's strategy, which we think all the more intelligently direct and numerically wonderful. It is worth-referenced that our investigation can be applied to two-dimensional Navier-Stokes conditions combined with heat diffusion conditions on limited areas. It should be simple for intrigued perusers to supply the essential subtleties.

The Primitive conditions and their varieties are that we restate some Sobolev type imbalances, uniform Gronwall disparity and some significant numerical outcomes on Primitive conditions. The worldwide in time presence of the arrangement and a vital boundedness lemma are expressed and demonstrated. At long last, we state and demonstrate our primary hypotheses. Investigation for different spaces, such as the round shell area or unbounded area, should be tended to elsewhere.

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Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

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